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Crusaders

Please use our right-hand navigation to explore the profiles of our independent crusaders.

Crusaders are listed by expedition leader, with expedition participants being slightly indented.

The amount of information that exists varies considerably depending on the individual crusader. For the more well documented crusaders we have included a short biography, but for many we only know the minor details of their departures for the east.

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